

Archaeology and sound preservation: Analysis of *Sgorgo N* by Pierluigi Billone

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Abstract

The music of Pierluigi Billone (1960) represents an exploration where composition becomes a means of musical invention, grounded in a deep understanding of the acoustic potential of instruments. His compositional approach appears to avoid electroacoustic thinking — not through explicit rejection, but as a consequence of an aesthetic privileging direct, corporeal engagement with sound. Nonetheless, the frequent use of the electric guitar, and its particular integration into his musical language, suggests his work reflects on electroacoustic aesthetics. Billone's *Sgorgo* trilogy (2012-2013) for solo electric guitar provides fertile ground for this inquiry. Among these large-scale works, *Sgorgo N* (2013), an intimate tribute to Luigi Nono (1924-1990), distinguishes itself by its exclusive use of the left hand on a single string, producing subtle electroacoustic sound qualities that invite extended, immersive listening. Analyzing this piece from a performance perspective reveals significant insights into the conception of musical sound, highlighting electroacoustic performance as an interdisciplinary practice encompassing instrumental technique, sonic perception, and embodied interaction.

1. Introduction

The scarce literature published to date on the work of Pierluigi Billone (1960-), together with the general opinion of those who follow his work, tends to agree that expansion of instrumental possibilities is one of the main characteristics of his music¹. His practice is centered on the exploration of sound and is grounded in in-depth research into the acoustic nature of instruments, within an interdisciplinary framework that integrates composition and instrumental practice and draws on other fields of artistic knowledge. Within this context, the limited use of technological resources in his work may suggest an absence of electroacoustic concern². However, this impression is misleading. The function and specific sound construction of the e-guitar in large ensemble works³, and more clearly in trilogy *Sgorgo*

¹ In France, the only study dedicated to Pierluigi Billone's work was written by Laurent Feneyrou in 2013: Laurent Feneyrou, "Pierluigi Billone", Base de données, Brahms IRCAM, 2013, <http://brahms.ircam.fr/pierluigi-billone>.

² From the composer's catalogue, the only piece that includes electronics is *Staglio II E* (2018), for flute bass and electronics. Site of reference: <https://www.pierluigibillone.com/en/home/>. This piece was commissioned by Françoise and Jean-Philippe Billarant, dedicated to flutist Matteo Cesari, and premiered at the Centre Pompidou, in Paris, on June 15, 2019. Site of reference: <https://ressources.ircam.fr/fr/work/staglio-ii-e>.

³ Of fifty-six pieces composed in the period 1989-2024, eleven include the electric guitar, three are for electric guitar solo and one for electric guitar duo. Site of reference: <https://www.pierluigibillone.com/en/home/>.

(2012-2013), for solo e-guitar reveal how acoustic, analog and digital treatments form intrinsic elements of an electroacoustic imagery. The aim of this article is to shed light on these elements through a synthesized analysis of *Sgorgo N* (2013), the third piece of the trilogy, focusing on the constitution of sound, its hybrid notation, the transposition of expressive vocality and its formalization in monody.

Although the *performance studies* have been established in academic discourse for a long time, the performance of electroacoustic music as primary subject appears to have been addressed only relatively recently⁴. This article examines two complementary perspectives within this theoretical framework, exploring their implications for both compositional and performance practices while engaging with existing research on questions arising from these two disciplines⁵. The first perspective is historical and consists in reviewing specific issues such as the questioning of the interdisciplinary nature of electroacoustic music⁶, the elements of performance culture⁷, critical review of concepts⁸ or the role of the performer⁹. The other perspective is related directly to the creative process, focusing specifically on subjects such as the relationship between composition, performance and improvisation¹⁰, and the interrogations that arise at the conceptual level within the framework of research on instrumental gesture¹¹. The article adopts four complementary methodological perspectives. It first considers instrumental, electroacoustic, and mixed music as coexisting sonic dimensions through which a single work may be interpreted. It then develops a comparative examination of notational strategies to investigate their employment within electroacoustic contexts. This is followed by a study of how vocal practices from popular music serve as a source of expressive strategies for writing. Finally, it addresses structural parameters, such as monodic organization, to clarify the interaction between instrumental and electroacoustic approaches to composition. Through this framework, the article engages with ongoing debates surrounding electroacoustic music as an interdisciplinary field and seeks to illuminate recent shifts in contemporary aesthetic orientations. Current research emphasizes not only the sonic qualities generated by hybrid instruments but also the stabilization of modes of writing through notational strategies adapted for music transmission. From this perspective, the analysis offers insight into the implications of the interaction between technical and aesthetic traditions in the early decades of the twenty-first century.

⁴ Germán Toro and Lucas Bennett, ed., *The Performance Practice of Electroacoustic Music: The Studio Di Fonologia Years*, Zürcher Musikstudien 10 (Peter Lang, 2018), 7.

⁵ José Luis Ferreira, "Interprétation de la Musique mixte - transfert de technologie, authenticité et fidélité : étude de cas du développement de la version temps réel d'Inharmonique (1977) de Jean Claude Risset", trad. João Svidzinski, *Revue Francophone d'Informatique et Musique*, n° 9 (septembre 2023).

⁶ Toro and Bennett, *The Performance Practice of Electroacoustic Music*, 7.

⁷ Kevin Dahan and Martin Laliberté, "Réflexions autour de la question d'interprétation de la musique électroacoustique", *Journées d'Informatique Musicale*, 2008, 7; Toro and Bennett, *The Performance Practice of Electroacoustic Music*, 7.

⁸ Toro and Bennett, *The Performance Practice of Electroacoustic Music*, 11.

⁹ Pascal Michel, "Le Studio Instrumental : Les données d'une virtuosité à l'intérieur même du son", in *Les nouveaux gestes de la musique*, edited by H. Genevois and Raphaël de Vivo, Collection Eupalinos (Parenthèses, 1999).

¹⁰ Dahan and Laliberté, "Réflexions autour de la question d'interprétation de la musique électroacoustique".

¹¹ Mariano Agustín Fernández, *L'interprétation dans la Musique Électroacoustique à travers de l'analyse de "Yaguai" pour Berimbau, Wii-rimbao et électronique* (Éditions Universitaires Européennes, 2010).

2. Flow in the dimensions of musical sound

Since e-guitar is a complex instrument allowed to produce sounds with of an acoustic, analogic and digital nature, it is essential to begin this analyze with the sonic dimensions of *Sgorgo N* in order to localized it in an historical and aesthetical context.

2.1. Instrumental dimension

There are three determining factors regarding the behavior of the strings and how they are played, which are limited to the acoustic nature of the instrument. On the instructions page, the composer prescribes an unorthodox tuning, with an interval of perfect fifth for the strings 6th to 4th (B₂-F₃-C₄), and an interval of diminished and perfect fourths for the strings 3th to 1th (F₄-B₄-E₅)¹². The reason of this relation is uncertain but one hypothesis would be that this disposition prevents resonance of the strings 6th-4th and 3th-1th through empathy and thereby possible disturbances in the device that synthesizes the sound. The principle established for the functioning of the hands is that the left hand is used exclusively to produce almost all sounds and the right hand is used to activate and operate the whammy bar. This technique is used to bend pitch downward a quarter tone to a minor third, or, in some cases, to bend pitch upward a semitone or even a whole tone. Finally, some other techniques are described such as a lightly tap on the string with the right index finger at the bridge in order to produce a vibration just before opening the volume pedal, pressure on the string at the level of the pegbox and the nut, scratch strings 5th and 6th with the edge of the finger, or even the use of both hands in a mixed technic between *tapping* and *glissando*. Indeed, Billone's compositional thinking takes into account the heritage of sensitivity and physical abilities that the instrument development process incorporates. That allows him establishes a starting point between instrumental practice heritage and the space that opens up the composition to new possibilities. Is in that sense that instrumental practice is understood as a sensitive organism¹³.

2.2. Electroacoustic dimension

At least four elements contribute to the electroacoustic dimension of this piece¹⁴: the electric system of the guitar body, the analog amplification system, and the digital system for effects processing. *Sgorgo N* requires an electric guitar with three single-coil pickups, enabling the generation of *electric hum*¹⁵. The preset configuration keeps the bridge pickup active, with the passband function attenuating high frequencies. Regarding amplification, although the score does not specify a model, the *Fender Twin* has become a conventional choice, as it is better

¹² The tuning of the e-guitar in *Sgorgo N* differs from traditional tuning by fourths or other alternatives such as re-stringing or open tunings. For e-guitar tunings see: Seth F. Josel and Michelle Lou, *The Techniques of E-Guitar Playing*, 1st ed. 2025 (Bärenreiter-Verlag, 2025), 114-21; Mike Frenkel, *The unorthodox guitar: a guide to alternative performance practice* (Oxford University Press, 2017).

¹³ FENEYROU, *op. cit.* (note 1).

¹⁴ For practical purposes in this paper the use of the term "electroacoustic" refers to the constitution of the system device of the e-guitar and not its historic connotation. Stéphane Roy and Jean-Jacques Nattiez, *L'analyse des musiques électroacoustiques : modèles et propositions*, Univers musical (l'Harmattan, 2003); François Delalande, "Le paradigme électroacoustique", in *Musiques du XXe Siècle*, vol. 1, Musiques, une encyclopédie pour le XXIe siècle (Actes sud/Cité de la musique, 2003).

¹⁵ The "electric hum" is defined as a sound associated with alternating current that is twice the frequency of the electrical grid.

suited to the composer's sound research. For the multi-effects processor, the specified model is the BOSS GT-10. The effects include three synthesis effects (*Slow Gear*, *Wave Synth*, *Octaver*), two time-delay effects (*Chorus*, *Delay*), a reverberation effect, and two additional programs for dynamic control (*Overdrive* and *Powered equalization*). In summary, the electroacoustic character of the work relies on an amplification system, filters, and an analog dynamic range transformation system, combine with a digital suite of electroacoustic techniques¹⁶.

2.3. Mixed dimension

The hybrid nature of the e-guitar and its complex constitution defines a sonic field that could be integrated into the reflection on mixed music, since it crystallizes a series of common relationships for combining acoustic and electronic components¹⁷. Nevertheless, the tools of analyze proposed for mixed music does not allow us to explain the phenomenon this interaction in *Sgorgo N*, since these are not autonomous components pretending to be one, but rather an intrinsic part of a single element. Indeed, this work deals with a condition related to electroacoustics that determines and conditions purely instrumental operation and vice versa: the synthesis techniques require a specific type of attack on the string, stability, pressure level, and imposes limits on the number of strings played simultaneously connected to a specific use of the whammy bar. This specificity is the starting point for understanding the role that e-guitar plays in Billone's reflection as a real-time electroacoustic medium. It is not just an amplified instrument or an instrument with electroacoustic possibilities; it occupies a central place in the compositional project because it has been configured on the margins of an aesthetic that seeks innovation in musical language through instrumental exploration.

3. Music notation constellations

The strategies of notation employed by Billone show a crossover between symbolic, graphic, and tablature, belonging to the Western tradition. However, his writing also incorporates resources from the Tibetan Buddhist tradition to operate in a hybrid notation adapted to the nature of the sound and the aesthetic orientation.

3.1. Western notation

During the XX century the effort of composers to renew the articulation of sound and the necessity to adapt symbolic notation to new practices and sonorities of electroacoustic instruments produce the transformation of notation systems¹⁸. In *Sgorgo N*, the predominant notational system is symbolic, serving to represent pitch, duration, timbre, and intensity. Nevertheless, to address electroacoustic sound, Billone employs an adapted system based on the graphic representation of modulating waves, similar to the notation used by Beatriz

¹⁶ Roads, *L'audio numérique : musique et informatique.*, 2nd edition, traduction by Jean de Reydellet (Dunod, 2007).

¹⁷ Philippe Lalitte, "Topo-Analyse de la musique mixte", in *Analyser la musique mixte*, edited by Alain Bonardi et al., Collection Pensée Musicale, edited by Jean-Michel Bardez (Delatour France, 2017), 24.

¹⁸ Jesús. Villa-Rojo, *Notazione e grafia musicale nel XX secolo*, edited by Karen Odobna Gerardi (Zecchini, 2013).

Ferreira (1937-) in *The U.F.O. Forest* (1998)¹⁹. This graphic strategy is used to indicate oscillators and sound-production media, but also to represent temporal phenomena such as the acceleration and deceleration of beats associated with the approach or departure of specific intervals, as well as the resonance generated by the amplifier when minimal pressure is applied to the string. This same system proves to be efficient for indicate mechanical operations such as the use of the *octaver* pedal (indicating the arrival interval in relation to the starting pitch), or the technique for scraping strings with the fingernails of the right hand (necessary to produce the characteristically distortion of digital synths). From pages eight to eleven, the treatment of sound changes and for that the composer uses the tablature system to describe with precision the level of pressure of the left hand on the 6th string, but also to indicate the distortion quality of sound or the suspended sound of the long-term resonances. A particular element in this section is that on the top of the tablature the composer adds a type of *neumatic* system to illustrate the legato form of the phrases, pointing out a mnemotechnic function of the score.

3.2. Tibetan Buddhist notation

Studies conducted by composer and researcher Ivan Vandor (1932-2020) on Tibetan music in the 1970s allow us to understand the hybridized notation in *Sgorgo N*²⁰. As pointed out in these studies, the vocal (*Yang* style) and instrumental style of writing in this tradition contains common elements such as wavy lines, writing in black ink, use of colors (red and yellow), syllables accompanying the strokes with mystical significance or to refer to interpretive aspects²¹. Another element is that the score is not a prescriptive notation as in the West, but rather a mnemonic script with some descriptive aspects²². For instrumental music, graphic elements, names of the notes or formulas represented graphically, or even syllables magic-religious or explanations for execution are frequently used²³.

Now then, comparing the notation of *Sgorgo N* with that of the Tibetan Buddhist tradition, significant similarities can be noted. First, the wavy lines representing voice modulations in Tibetan music resemble the modulations of the e-guitar sound in *Sgorgo N*, shaped by the use of the whammy bar and amplified by microtonal modulations produced around the unison interval. It seems that this resource functions as a link to the vocal quality of some type of singing. Second, the use of black ink that characterized the handwritten scores in Tibetan Buddhist music. In Billone's scores, even those with large instrumental ensembles, are also characterized by the use of black ink in his handwriting. In fact, the published versions of his scores are all copies of the manuscripts, dispensing with the digital music notation programs frequently used today. Third, the syllables accompanying the wavy lines that refer to aspects of musical performance in the Tibetan tradition adhere, in *Sgorgo N*, to the Western tradition of prescribing instrumental and interpretive performance actions. The notation in Billone's

¹⁹ Villa-Rojo, *Notazione e grafia musicale nel XX secolo*, 324.

²⁰ Ivan Vandor, "Cymbals and Trumpets from the "Roof of the World"", *Music Educators Journal* 61, n° 1 (1974): 106-109+145-146; Ivan Vandor, "Tibetan Musical Notation", *The World of Music* 17, n° 2 (1975): 3-7; Ivan Vandor, "Aesthetics and Ritual Music. Some Remarks with Reference to Tibetan Music", *The World of Music* 18, n° 2 (1976): 29-32; Ivan Vandor, *Musique du Bouddhisme Tibétain*, Les traditions musicales, edited by Alain Daniélou (Éditions Buchet/Chastel, 1976).

²¹ Vandor, *Musique du Bouddhisme Tibétain*, 115-16.

²² Vandor, *Musique du Bouddhisme Tibétain*, 117.

²³ Vandor, *Musique du Bouddhisme Tibétain*, 119-20.

music is extremely detailed, including not only symbolic elements referring to the different components of musical sound, but also verbal descriptions accompanied by descriptive images. Finally, the use of colors. In several writings, Vandor points out the different variations in the use of color in Buddhist scores²⁴. He describes, for example, that in the Ganden Chöpel Ling monastery, the color red in the notation indicates the parts of the text that should be sung by the ritual leader, while in the Gyütö monastery, the red and yellow lines are purely decorative²⁵. Although no color code is used in *Sgorgo N*, in other works Billone uses colors to differentiate between different sound qualities. For example, in *KE.AN-Cerchio* (1995-2003), for bass voice, the use of colors allows for the differentiation of vocal techniques — intonation with full resonance, intonation with air vibration, intonation with a very nasal vibration. In conclusion, beyond the parallels found in the notation itself, what the comparative study reveals is the spiritual dimension evoked by Billone's music, projected as a set of diverse associations with Tibetan Buddhist music: tantric chanting, the use of low registers supported by harmonic sounds, the figure of the monk-musician²⁶, and the practice of meditation and spiritual exercise²⁷.

4. Anatomy of expression

An essential element of poetics in the work of Billone is the expression transmitted through vocality. Although part of the expressive source of *Sgorgo N* lies in its connection with Tibetan Buddhist tradition, it is in American popular music where this emotional element in the compositional technique can be perceived. In 2023, during a long conversation held at his residence in Vienna, the composer reveals the mechanism of perception that allows him to articulate expression in his writing. In that encounter, the composer quoted two songs by the American singer-songwriter Tom Waits (1949): "Blue Valentine" and "Kentucky Avenue" both included in the album *Blue Valentine* (1978). The first example foregrounds expressive aspects of singer vocal diction — such as the sounds "ff" or "pf"²⁸ — situated within a plaintive register. It also brings out techniques characteristic of blue-jazz vocality, including vibrato and vocal distortion (growling). Billone's analysis focuses on this repertoire of vocal sounds and noises, through which the voice articulates an expression of sorrow. The second example illustrates the subtle vibrato at the end of some phrases, which extends and gains in amplitude and duration over the course of the song²⁹. This tiny element is the object of reflection in the composer's perception and is important insofar as it places it as a key point of analytical listening. For this kind of elements, the metaphor of the "eclipse" is useful to him in emphasizing a point in the space of a long musical timeline that stands out from others due to its expressive specificity. Rather than pointing to the extinction or disappearance of light, the image attempts to bring to the fore a brief but significant moment within the luminous continuum. The above examples showcase the expressive cell that relates to perception and

²⁴ Vandor, "Cymbals and Trumpets from the "Roof of the World""; Vandor, "Tibetan Musical Notation"; Vandor, *Musique du Bouddhisme Tibétain*.

²⁵ Vandor, *Musique du Bouddhisme Tibétain*, 117.

²⁶ Ivan Vandor, "The Musician in the Tibetan Traditional Society", *The World of Music* 21, n° 2 (1979): 39-45.

²⁷ Vandor, "Cymbals and Trumpets from the "Roof of the World"".

²⁸ This specific sound appears at minute 01:26.

²⁹ This subtle vibrato on the letter "n" appears specifically in the next moments of the song: 0:30, 0:41, 0:54, 0:58, 1:14, 1:30, 1:33, 1:35, 1:38, 1:43, 1:47, 2:00, 2:03, 2:16, 2:20, 2:33, 2:37, 2:53, 3:05, 3:10, 3:37, 3:46, 3:54, 3:59, 4:09, 4:18.

encapsulates the material from which instrumental and scriptural technique develops. Vocal reference achieved through mechanical resources reaches its level of technical mastery when vocal expression emerges from the instrumental, exactly as in "Brush With The Blues" (1999) of the American electric guitarist Jeff Beck (1944-2023). Indeed, of this instrumental song Billone closely observe the set of manual operations performed by the instrumentalist that allow them to imitate the vocal modulations found in traditional blues singing: use of the vibrato bar for the vocal vibrato technique, fingernails and fingers to strike the strings and produce sounds for the imitation of growling. The tool Billone uses to understand the anatomy of expression in popular music is a type of perceptual analysis, as it is essentially based on listening and audiovisual observation. It is a type of systematic analysis that moves away from musicological approaches, focusing on sensitive elements and the operational modalities of the hands on the instrument. In other words, this approach seeks to understand the technical functioning of expression and seeks to highlight aspects of sound that escape general perception: it is about listening to what lies behind and within the sound itself. From the point of view of the creative process, this exploration of the sensitive through instrumental gestures contrasts with the use of specialized literature on instrumental techniques, given its limited scope in terms of openness and the search for creative solutions. Nor is it a question of imitating techniques from popular traditions in order to develop them in an adapted context, but rather of using them as a starting point for an autonomous search through the exploration of their possibilities. From the observation of these musical moments, Billone follows a method that goes from attentive listening to imitation and understanding of the technical mechanism of sound production through reflection.

5. Mechanics of vocality

The expressive vocality that that characterizes this music emerges at the margins of the melodic line. A segmental analysis of the first page of the score reveals immanent features of the writing that are closely link to the hybrid nature of both sound and formal conception: the melodic contour of monodic singing; zones of harmonic stability and instability; the shaping of the instrumental sound profile through the four stages of envelope articulation used in electroacoustic sound production (attack, decay, sustain, release)³⁰; and the manual, mechanical, and technological operations involved at different levels of sound generation that modifies the conventional body disposition.

³⁰ Roads, *L'audio numérique*, 358.

5.1. First segment

Figure 1: *Sgorgo N* (page 1, system 1) analyze of first segment³¹.

From the outset, and within a short time span, several layers of complexity emerge:

1. Instrumental techniques: right-hand *tapping* with the volume pedal closed to conceal the string attack, combinations of *tapping* and *glissando* executed with both hands, sequences of attacks on the same fret using different fingers to produce micro-intervallic variations, and light right-hand taps that set the string into vibration.
2. Mechanical operations: pitch modulation achieved through the expression pedal, used to control the *octaver* effect.
3. Melodic profile: a range limited to one octave, articulated through continuous fluctuations that emphasize an intermediate zone of micro-intervallic instability.

³¹ Note: It is important to point out that the pitches indicated in the score of *Sgorgo N* do not represent the actual pitches. The notation indicates the position of the fingers on the frets equivalent to the pitches indicated in conventional tuning and conventional guitar notation (transposition of one octave). Each of the diagrams presented in this article shows the written note and the real pitch.

5.2. Second segment

The figure shows a musical score for the second segment of *Sgorgo N*. It consists of three staves: 'Pulsation with right hand', 'Resonance', and 'Pedal expression'. The 'Pulsation with right hand' staff has a tempo marking of quarter note = 60. The 'Resonance' staff has a 'held' marking. The 'Pedal expression' staff has a 'no beats' marking. The 'end of the segment' part shows a final note with a '6' marking. The score is annotated with various markings and arrows indicating specific performance techniques.

Figure 2: *Sgorgo N* (page 1, system 1-2), analyze of second segment.

Two operations can be distinguished in second segment, with the particularity that they are performed during the resonance time of the two stimulated strings (5th and 6th) at the precedent segment. First, the sequence of *tapping* of left hand on the 6th string and light tap of right hand on the 5th string to make them vibrate simultaneously. Second, the pressure variations of the left hand on the 6th string to modulate the beats. The melodic profile consists of a series of modulations of a semitone distance around the pivot note C#₂ (controlled by the *octaver* pedal), and in the splitting of the monody from the unison interval, exploiting the beats produced by slight variations in pitch generated simultaneously by the electroacoustic configuration system and the different levels of pressure on the string.

5.3. Third segment:

Figure 3: *Sgorgo N* (page 1, system 2), analyze of third segment (diagram 1).

Figure 4: *Sgorgo N* (page 1, system 2), analyze of third segment (diagram 2).

The two diagrams in segment three once again illustrate the combination of instrumental and electroacoustic operations developed at a higher level of complexity than before: melodic fluctuation around a pivot note, and regions of micro-intervallic stability and instability. This segment also allows us to identify that these operations occur within the framework of the

four phases of the ADSR (attack, decay, sustain, release) envelope generator³², which would suggest that this type of phrase is constructed based on an understanding of synthesized sound nature.

5.4. Fourth segment

Figure 5: *Sgorgo N* (page 1, system 3) analyzed of fourth segment.

In this segment, a distinctive right-hand technique enables the production of rhythmically controlled beats through pitch variation within a unison interval. Also noteworthy is the controlled use of the volume pedal as a mechanical means of shaping the amplitude of the output signal. To recap, when the four segments are considered together, a global profile emerges in which fluctuations and pitch bifurcations give rise to micro-intervallic harmonic phenomena:

Analyze of first page: melodic profile of the monody.

The examination of this initial section elucidates essential elements of the lyrical and ritualistic character that will be developed throughout the work, but it also illustrates the way

³² Thomas D. Rossing et al., *The Science of Sound*, 3th ed., Pearson New International Edition, Always Learning (Pearson Education, 2014), 626.

in which Billone operates with elementary elements such as the monodic line. Furthermore, what is deciphered in this section of *Sgorgo N*, where different segments with a long duration resulting in an only phrase, is the idea of suspended singing, which in Luigi Nono's work translates into a relationship between points, lines, and fields, whose fabric forms fields of varying density³³.

6. Conclusions

Despite the need to reduce the analysis to synthetic elements, study of the four precedent points gives us some preliminary answers to the central question of this inquiry. The examination of the sound nature and instrumental configuration of *Sgorgo N* confirmed the complexity of its formal components and the pertinence to focus attention on aspects of performance. Notation is thus shown to be a flexible tool that could be adapted to the needs of the electroacoustic medium and the sonic material. The perceptive approach undertaken by Billone to understand the mechanisms of expression and the operational possibilities for their transposition into instrumental writing reveals an innovative approach of applied analysis. Segmental analysis of the monody and the melodic structure was useful in this regard because it provided insight into the musical, technical, mechanical, and mnemonic mechanisms involved in the formalization of music. Overall, the tribute to Luigi Nono is not limited to an anecdotal aspect of the work's title, but is also manifested at a structural level, establishing a link between the development of the sound material, its electroacoustic nature, and the strategy of suspended singing. It is also interesting to note how the creative process of this piece challenges conventional listening by directing sensory attention to elements often relegated to the background of musical experience. In doing so, it dislocates traditional listening categories and reconfigures instrumental technique through bodily experience, opening the way to a *dematerialization* and *embodiment* of sound — a response to the concept of sound plasticity, a central concern in contemporary compositional thought. In this sense, *Sgorgo N* generates a reflective space that challenges dominant notions of composition as a manipulation of materials.

In summary, the mode of listening required by this repertoire resembles an archaeological search, i.e., an uncovering of sensory traces eroded by the immediacy of our time and buried beneath categories that fossilize sonic experience. This pursuit unfolds on the margins of musical history, which often confines its sources to stylistic gestures within Western notation. Paradoxically, the archaic mode of listening suggested by this music draws not only on ancestral cultural references but also on the analytical and sensitive reexamination of contemporary sound practices — such as those of Tom Waits and Jeff Beck. This reading of musical culture contrasts with that of Billone's contemporary, Fausto Romitelli (1963–2004), whose reflection on the music of his time gave rise to an electric and electroacoustic conception of instrumental sound, and whose practice makes use of generic stylistic markers. In contrast, Billone's meticulous research into touch and the role of the hands revitalizes performance practice by distancing it from the notion of technique — or more precisely, "extended technique" — that treats sound as an operable object. This perspective opens the way to a conception distinct from the one prevailing in twentieth-century compositional thought, shaped largely by technological transformation.

³³ Martin Kaltenecker, "Le chant suspendu de Luigi Nono", in *L'expérience mélodique au XXe siècle* (Contrechamps Editions, 2024), 241.

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